

OPTIMUM THICKNESS OF JOINTS MADE OF GFRP PULTRUDED ADHERENDS AND POLYURETHANE ADHESIVE

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SUMMARY

This paper presents experimental and numerical investigations on double-lap joints composed of pultruded GFRP profiles and polyurethane adhesive subjected to quasi-static axial tensile loading. Joint strength was predicted using a probabilistic method. An optimum adhesive layer thickness for which joint strength is maximal was found, and joint strength consistently increases with the overlap length.

Keywords: Adhesive joints; GFRP; Strength; Probabilistic Methods; Optimum thickness.

INTRODUCTION

Adhesive bonding represents the most material-adapted and efficient method for joining pultruded glass fiber-reinforced (GFRP) components. However, at the present moment there are no generally accepted design codes or reliable strength prediction methods. Vallée et al. [1,2] presented a probabilistic method for the strength prediction of adhesively bonded lap joints from pultruded GFRP adherends and epoxy adhesive layers subjected to quasi-static axial tensile loading. The method is based on the statistical distribution of the GFRP material resistance, which was modeled using both Weibull and Generalized Lambda statistical distributions. Since the method provided a good agreement between strength predictions and failure loads of joints composed of GFRP pultruded adherends and stiff epoxy adhesive, it was decided to extend the research program to a different type of adhesive, namely, soft polyurethane adhesive.

Experimental investigations

The influence of the adhesive layer thickness (from 0.3 to 3.0 mm) and the overlap length (from 50 to 200 mm) on the joint behavior was analyzed, with regard to the load-displacement behavior, the failure modes (Fig. 1) and joint strength. It was found that (i) there is an optimum adhesive layer thickness of 1.0 mm, for which joint strength is maximal; and (ii) joint strength consistently increases with the overlap length.

Fig. 1: Crack propagation in mat layer along overlap of specimen DN200-1/2.

Numerical investigations

The complete length of the tested specimens was modeled using the finite element package ANSYS. This allowed gathering the through-thickness normal and shear stresses for varying adhesive thickness and overlap length, which were used as input in the strength prediction method.

Strength prediction

The strength of all tested joints was then predicted using the previously developed probabilistic method that includes a failure criterion based on the interaction between through-thickness tensile and shear stresses at the failure location. The method takes into consideration the scale sensitivity of strength, which was modeled using both a two-parameter Weibull distribution and a Generalized Lambda distribution. The method considers not only the magnitude of the stress fields, but also the volume over which stress peaks act.

References

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